

Compressive Strength, Impact and Hardness of Banana-sisal-Saw Dust NFCs Materials

¹Niharika Kumari, ²Baliram Prasad Singh, ³Sanjay Kumar Choudhary and ⁴Dipo Mahto

¹Lecturer, Department of Physics, Government Polytechnic Khagaria, India

²Associate Professor, Department of Chemistry, B. N. College Bhagalpur, India

³Vice Chancellor, L.N. Mithila University Darbhanga, India

⁴Principal, T. N. B. College Bhagalpur, India

⁴Prof. & Head(Ex), Department of Physics, Bhagalpur College of Engineering, India

Corresponding Author: Dipo Mahto

Abstract:

The present paper discusses the compressive, impact strength and hardness of banana – sisal - saw dust NFCs taking four samples of different compositions of banana, sisal and saw dust mixing with proper amount of reinforced epoxy materials, which concludes that both the strength like the compressive as well as the impact showing to decrease, when the content of the sawdust is considered in decreasing manner and vice-versa.

Keywords:

Compressive Strength, Izod impact and Hardness

1. Introduction:

The NFs are of many types like sisal, banana, luffa, date plant etc. and found in abundance in our country. They have low density. They are renewable, eco-friendly, durable, biodegradable, recyclable and available at low cost in the village market and also taken from agriculture and forest [1-4]. Kumari R. et al. have discussed the tensile and flexural properties of banana – sisal - saw dust NFCs, which concluded that both the strength decreases with decreasing the saw dust content [5]. The hybrid composite materials have been developed by the use of a bio-epoxy resin matrix reinforced with the natural banana-sisal fibres [6]. The tensile, compressive, flexural, and impact strength and Brinell hardness increase by the increase of the sawdust with proper mixing of the epoxy matrix has been studied [7].

In this paper, we have discussed the compressive, impact as well as hardness of the banana-sisal-saw dust NFCS taking four samples of different compositions mixed in the proper amount of reinforced epoxy, which concludes that increasing the sawdust in the materials, both the tensile and flexural strength also increase.

2. Materials & Method:

Four samples shown in the following table of the required components with certain amount of reinforced epoxy composite materials are taken into consideration for testing in accordance with ASTM D570 standard.

The percentage amount of the components of samples is taken as:

Table: 1.

S. No.	Sample	Banana (in %)	Sisal (in %)	Sawdust (in %)
1.	S1	80	15	5
2.	S2	75	15	10
3.	S3	65	20	15
4.	S4	60	20	20

Each sample is individually bounded with eighty percent (80%) epoxy resin to follow the ASTM Standard. The SEM of each sample is obtained and after this, fibre-matrix interface and also properties are studied..

3. Mechanical Properties:

The following table shows the mechanical properties of four samples using UTM to follow the ASTM Standard.

Table: 2.

Sample	Mechanical Properties			Remarks
	Compressive Strength (in M Pa)	Impact Strength (in K J / m ²)	Hardness (in M Pa)	
S-1	241.50	31.25	25.75	All the mechanical properties discussed increase with increasing the amount of the saw dust in the NFC materials and vice-versa.
S-2	241.90	31.95	26.40	
S-3	242.80	32.10	26.95	
S-4	243.50	32.80	27.20	

4. Figure.1:**Fig. 1: Compressive Strength of required reinforced epoxy NFCs.**

Figure.2:

Fig. 2: Impact of required reinforced epoxy composites.

Figure.3:

Fig. 3: Hardness of required material.

5. Result & Discussions:

The present research paper discusses the strength of compressive test, impact test and hardness test of NFCs formed by Banana, Sisal and Sawdust materials in a proper ratio as discussed in the table 1 of this current paper. The NFCs formed of samples S1, S 2, S 3 and S 4 are tested by UTM to follow the ASTM D695. The observed data are collected and all the data are listed in the table 2. The observation shows that these strengths of the NFCs increase by increase of sawdust content. The sample S1 (241.5MPa) for all these test are found lower, when compared with the compressive strength of composites.

The observation of the figures 1, 2 and 3 also observes that the compressive, impact and hardness of NFCs is increasing after adding the sawdust materials

The above discussion concludes that when the sawdust is reduced in the composites, it enhances all the strengths of the testing NFCs and compared with the data of the references [9 – 10]. This comparative study of our work gives the support the suitability of materials.

6. Conclusions:

The compressive strength, Izod impact and hardness strength all increase with increasing the amount of the saw dust in the NFCs and vice-versa.

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